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Exploring the Socio-religious and Human Development Implications of Combating Illicit Drug Use in Contemporary Nigerian Society

Samuel Olamide ADEKOYA

*Department of Christian Religious Studies and
Philosophy, Faculty of Humanities, Redeemer's
University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria*
adekoya13821@run.edu.ng, +2348034708321,
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0550-3107>

Adediran Idowu SEGUN

*Department of Christian Religious Studies and
Philosophy, Faculty of Humanities, Redeemer's
University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria*
segunfunmiade@gmail.com, +2348036893088,
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0617-6477>

Prof. Afolorunso Olalekan DAIRO

*Department of Christian Religious Studies and
Philosophy, Faculty of Humanities, Redeemer's
University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria*
dairoafolorunsho@run.edu.ng, +2348034001020,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3865-1266>

Abstract

This study explores the socio-religious and human development implications of combating illicit drug use in Nigeria, examining the factors that influence drug involvement and its societal consequences. Illicit drug use threatens public health, social stability, and national development. Despite existing laws, the role of socio-cultural and religious factors in substance misuse remains poorly understood, with gaps in effective interventions and research. This study aims to bridge these gaps by exploring how socio-cultural and religious dynamics combating drug abuse, particularly among youth,

and assessing the effectiveness of interventions, including faith-based approaches, in prevention and recovery. The study employs a mixed-method approach of integrating historical and content analysis of qualitative methods, based on Rational Choice Theory, by Cesare Beccaria, to explore decision-making in substance use. The findings highlight peer influence and socio-economic challenges as key factors driving drug use, while faith-based interventions have proven successful in encouraging abstinence and supporting rehabilitation. Drug abuse harms development, while current responses lack cultural fit, calling for a more integrated, community-based approach. Recommendations include strengthening community-based drug prevention programs, enhancing faith-based partnerships, implementation of public education and awareness campaigns targeting youth, investment in socio-economic support programs for vulnerable populations and establishment of comprehensive rehabilitation and mental health services. These efforts will enhance public health systems, strengthen Nigerian government institutions, and bolster resilience within families and communities. Additionally, this research will make a meaningful contribution to academic knowledge and scholarship.

Keywords: Faith-based Interventions, Illicit Drug Use, Rehabilitation and Mental Health, Socio-Religious Dynamics, Youth and Peer Influence

Introduction

Illicit drug consumption presents a significant challenge in contemporary Nigerian society, threatening public health, destabilising social structures, and impeding national development. Despite various efforts to tackle drug abuse in Nigeria, the issue remains unresolved, jeopardising societal stability and human development. In Nigeria, commonly abused substances with psychoactive and health-related impacts include cannabis, alcohol, sedatives, stimulants, and opioids. These substances can cause various health issues, including psychosis, requiring treatment in hospitals or rehabilitation centres (Haruna & Dukku, 2019, p. 2). Basically, illicit drugs are substances, apart from food, that alter the structure or function of a living organism through chemical means (Ksir, Hart & Ray, 2008, p. 5), the intricate relationship between socio-religious factors and human development highlights the urgency for comprehensive and multidimensional solutions. Also, the absence of socio-religious frameworks in current intervention programs and the lack of research on their potential impact reveal a significant gap. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the socio-religious and development implications of combating illicit drug

abuse and offering sustainable strategies for prevention and rehabilitation. It covers an analysis of drug abuse within Nigeria's varied socio-religious context, emphasising its effects on individuals, families, and communities. The significance of this research lies in its potential to inform policymakers, faith-based organisations, and community leaders, offering practical, culturally sensitive solutions to address this critical societal issue.

Aims and Objectives

- i. To examine how major religious traditions in Nigeria perceive and respond to illicit drug use and their influence on public opinion and policy.
- ii. To assess the effects of drug abuse on key human development areas such as education, employment, mental health, and social stability.
- iii. To explore the role and impact of faith-based interventions in drug rehabilitation and social reintegration.
- iv. To analyse existing state and non-state strategies against drug use in relation to cultural and religious values.
- v. To develop a holistic intervention model that integrates socio-religious insights, human development goals, and policy frameworks.

Methodology

The paper employs the historical and content analysis of qualitative research methodology to explore the socio-religious and developmental impacts of illicit drug use in Nigeria, focusing on its causes, effects, and community-driven solutions.

Research Questions

- i. How do religious traditions in Nigeria view drug use, and how do these views influence public opinion and policy?
- ii. What are the effects of drug abuse on education, employment, mental health, and social stability in Nigeria?
- iii. How effective are faith-based groups in drug rehabilitation and reintegration efforts?
- iv. How do government and non-government organisations (NGO) strategies align or conflict with Nigeria's religious and cultural values?
- v. What are the key elements that are needed for a culturally rooted and sustainable intervention model against drug use?

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this paper is grounded in Rational Choice Theory, by Cesare Beccaria, which suggests that individuals weigh costs and benefits before acting. In drug use, it also explains how people evaluate rewards like pleasure against risks such as health issues and legal consequences. Peer influence, substance availability, and sibling interactions greatly affect substance use. Kuntsche and Jordan (2006) and Lungborg (2006, pp. 167–174) stress that "peer associations with substance users greatly influence the onset and progression of drug dependence".

The Consumption of Illicit Drugs in Contemporary Nigerian Society

In Nigeria, common illicit drugs include cannabis, which remains widely used despite being illegal, alongside heroin, cocaine, and methamphetamine, which are more prevalent in urban areas. Psychoactive substance use in Africa began with traditional drugs like alcohol, cannabis, and khat, but expanded with prescription drugs and increased trafficking of heroin and cocaine (Odejide, 2006, pp. 87–102). Khat is a plant from East Africa and the Arabian Peninsula, whose leaves contain a stimulant called cathinone, producing effects like alertness, energy, and euphoria. However, in Nigeria, kolanut serves a similar stimulant role as khat. It contains caffeine and theobromine, boosting alertness and energy, and holds cultural and religious significance among major ethnic groups. In Nigeria, drug use is estimated to affect 14.4% of the population, approximately 14.3 million people, with cannabis being the most commonly used drug, followed by opioids, particularly the non-medical use of prescription opioids and cough syrup (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2018, p. 8). However, the illicit drug dependence can manifest both psychologically and physically, with prolonged use leading to both forms of dependence (WHO, 2014). Prescription drugs like tramadol and codeine are also frequently misused, exacerbating the country's growing drug abuse issue. These substances affect a broad demographic, especially youth and vulnerable populations, leading to severe social and health consequences.

Furthermore, the abuse of inhalants, such as glue and petrol, is widespread in certain rural areas and among marginalised youth. Traditional substances like *kolanut*, *zakami*, *hankufa*, *auguru* (snuff), and *gagai* are known for their stimulant effects on users. Additionally, emerging

substances such as *gadagi*, a tea or drink containing various stimulating components, are increasingly popular among Nigerian youth, particularly in Kano (Abdullahi, 2003). Furthermore, researchers have observed that *Gadagi* has a high caffeine content (Sulaiman, 2000, p. 27). These traditional stimulants boost alertness, wakefulness, and concentration, creating effects, similar to those of other illicit drugs. Emerging substances, such as lizard excretion and pit latrine odours, are also becoming increasingly popular among the youth, despite unclear effects. However, these substances are known to alter users' psychological and biochemical states (Abdullahi, 1997). The easy availability of these drugs, combined with socio-economic hardships and inadequate regulation, has intensified the drug abuse crisis. As demand for these substances rises, so too do the associated risks, including addiction, health deterioration, and social instability.

Prescription drug abuse, particularly of tramadol and codeine, has significantly risen in recent years, especially among young people. Drug abuse refers to the excessive use of substances, leading to harmful behaviour and negative consequences for both the user and society. Its impact extends beyond the individual and their immediate community, causing widespread consequences for society at large (Garba, Okorie & Hassan, 2020, pp. 237-240). Drug abuse is driven by peer pressure, curiosity, and ignorance, with users seeking acceptance, experimenting, and being unaware of the risks. Lack of education, skills, and difficulty adjusting to urban life also contribute to isolation and further drug use (Caday, 2017, p. 3422). Adamson and Akindele (1994, pp. 105–108) and Gureje et al. (2007, pp. 1–9) highlight that "the substance abuse's effect on mental health and society in Nigeria. The first nationwide survey reports 14.4% (14.3 million) of Nigerians aged 15-64 use substances". Mental health experts observe that most psychiatric cases are drug-induced, with substance use now a leading cause of mental illness and rising at an alarming rate (Oguizu & Oguizu, 2023, pp. 46–47). Undoubtedly, it is a significant public health issue, with relationships and social environments playing crucial roles in its prevalence, while, social media further influences attitudes and behaviours by shaping online interactions (Hanson et al., 2013, p. 189). These drugs are readily accessible and commonly misused for their psychoactive effects, leading to addiction and exacerbating the country's drug abuse crisis. Their

widespread use not only damages individual health but also burdens Nigeria's healthcare system, public safety, and social stability.

Socio-Religious Dimensions of Illicit Drug Use in Nigeria

Cultural and religious attitudes in Nigeria generally view drug use as immoral and detrimental to society, emphasising values like self-discipline, family integrity, and communal responsibility. Despite these teachings, the widespread availability of drugs and socio-economic pressures have led to increased drug use, especially among youth. Substance abuse affects individuals across all social groups, but it primarily impacts the youth. Over the years, discussions have emphasised that those who engage in substance abuse are more prone to exhibiting antisocial behaviours as a direct result of their drug use (Vitalis, Ugwuoke & Eze, 2024, p. 1-21). This is primarily attributed to the vulnerability factors associated with adolescence, such as stress from physical and physiological changes, a strong desire for peer acceptance, and the need to fit in both at school and within society (Oketch, 2008). Religion is deeply embedded in African society, influencing political and socio-economic activities through religious expressions and rituals (Agbiji & Swart, 2015, pp. 1–20). While religious leaders promote drug-free lifestyles through various initiatives, these efforts are often hindered by peer pressure, poverty, and social normalisation of drug use.

Faith-based organisations in Nigeria play a crucial role in combating drug abuse through counselling, rehabilitation, and spiritual guidance, promoting drug-free lifestyles and community support. Despite facing challenges like limited resources, stigma, and lack of coordination, they have made significant progress by raising awareness, offering culturally tailored services, and focusing on prevention. Nigerian norms and values, rooted in religion and upheld by divine sanctions, are integral to the country's socio-cultural system. However, moral decadence has emerged due to the neglect of religious education and these foundational values, which once ensured societal security (Okobia, Okafor & Osajie, 2016, p. 151-168). The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency Act Cap. N 30, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004, prescribes life imprisonment for those involved in trafficking cocaine, LSD, heroin, or similar drugs, while possession or use is punishable by 15 to 25 years in prison (Okongwu, Ejokemaimoisi, & Wakoby, 2023, p. 44-52). Despite the existence of laws, policies, and strategies, substance abuse continues to be a rising issue in Nigeria. To

make a greater impact, faith-based organisations must strengthen partnerships with the government and NGOs, while also advocating for increased funding and policy reforms to tackle both the spiritual and socio-economic factors driving drug abuse.

In Nigeria, the relationship between drug use and social values is influenced by cultural and religious beliefs that stress moral integrity, family unity, and community responsibility. While these values discourage drug abuse, peer pressure, media influence, and socio-economic challenges have led some, especially youth, to use drugs as a form of escape. Social media platforms facilitate easy access to drugs, including prescription medications. Moreover, teenagers who spend more time on these networks are five times more likely to use tobacco, three times more likely to drink alcohol, and twice as likely to use marijuana (Califano, 2004; Forman, 2003, p. 889-889). This disconnect between traditional values and modern influences calls for integrated solutions that address both psychological and socio-economic factors driving addiction.

The normalisation of drug use in some social circles, particularly in urban areas, complicates efforts to align social values with modern realities. Illicit drug use and dependence are strongly influenced by early life factors that heighten the risk of abuse, particularly cannabis use during late adolescence and early adulthood, being a key predictor of later use of other illicit drugs (Fergusson, Boden & Horwood, 2008, 165-177). Cannabis is easily accessible, and students played a role in its supply. Although, men were socially accepted in its use, but women faced stigma, often stopping due to marriage and societal pressures (Dumbili, 2020, p. 287). Although, religious institutions play a key role in promoting anti-drug messages, but to be effective, these efforts must also address underlying causes like poverty, unemployment, and limited education. Also, a holistic approach that combines moral teachings with practical support is crucial in combating drug abuse and reinforcing a drug-free culture.

Implications of Illicit Drug Use on Human Development

Drug abuse refers to using chemicals to induce pleasurable effects, often leading to dependency. It causes long-term bodily harm, and needle users are at risk of contracting HIV and hepatitis B and C (Mandal, 2019). Rising substance abuse among youth, especially alcohol and hookah (also known as shisha), is harming their mental health and is seen as a status symbol,

despite its serious personal and societal effects (Mukati, 2020, p. 362). Illicit drug use results in serious psychological and physical health issues, including addiction, depression, anxiety, and cognitive impairments, which can also, cause permanent damage to essential organs such as the liver, heart, and brain, and heighten the risk of infectious diseases, particularly through behaviours like needle sharing. These health impacts not only affect the individual but also place a strain on healthcare systems and obstruct human development by diminishing productivity and the quality of life. Drug abuse is a critical social problem that deteriorates the quality of life (Maisto, Galizio & Connors, 2018), which can affect the body's functioning, with effects that may be positive or negative; however, they are largely destructive and harmful to humanity, with their adverse impact often extending to future generations.

According to the World Drug 2019 Report, approximately 35 million people worldwide were affected by drug use disorders and in need of treatment; an increase from the previous estimate of 30.5 million. Additionally, there were 585,000 drug-related deaths reported in 2017 (Onaolapo et al., 2022, p. 1268). Surveys and prospective studies show that drug use is highest between the ages of 18 and 25, with young people using substances more than older adults (Merikangas & McClair, 2012, p. 779–789). Consequently, the psychological effects of drug abuse can create a cycle of mental health problems, social isolation, and poor decision-making, further impairing the individual's ability to function effectively in the society. This often leads to negative consequences for families and communities, with strained relationships, higher caregiving demands, and increased poverty. Ultimately, these combined psychological and physical challenges impede human development, limiting opportunities for personal growth, education, and economic progress while perpetuating cycles of poverty and dysfunction. Substance use disorders (SUDs) lead to control issues, neglect of responsibilities, and health problems. Children of parents with SUDs face socio-economic, academic, and family challenges. Drug abuse is also associated with risky behaviours like early sex, violence, and delinquency (Rajeswari, 2021, p. 558). Most importantly, illicit drug use disrupts family structures, causing strained relationships, both emotional and financial burdens that negatively affect the well-being of children and dependents. This often leads to neglect, abuse, and behavioural issues in children, perpetuating cycles of poverty, instability, and social disintegration.

Additionally, the stigma surrounding drug addiction isolates families, hindering access to support and weakening community cohesion, which obstructs broader social and economic progress.

Neuroticism and impulsivity are the personality traits most closely associated with drug-dependent patients, playing a central role in the resulting model, although their connection seemed to follow a hierarchical order (Valero et al, 2014). Therefore, illicit drug use carries significant socioeconomic consequences, including decreased productivity, job loss, and rising healthcare costs, which place a heavy burden on both individuals and society. As drug dependence grows, individuals struggle to maintain their workforce participation, leading to economic instability and a depletion of human capital. On a broader scale, the economic impact of drug abuse is seen in higher crime rates, increased healthcare spending, and a demand for rehabilitation services, all of which stifle national development.

Significantly, drug abuse worsens poverty by limiting access to education and employment opportunities, crucial for upward mobility. Studies show that consistent use of heroin and cocaine is linked to higher crime rates, with the type and intensity of criminal behaviour varying among users, which impacts their economic empowerment (Ammerman et al., 1999, 13-30). Moreover, families impacted by addiction often face financial strain as funds are redirected to support the drug habit, creating a cycle of economic hardship. Also, the broader societal costs extend to law enforcement and social services, as communities contend with rising crime, homelessness, and the need for social interventions, which further strain resources and divert attention from other developmental priorities. Undoubtedly, the socioeconomic effects of drug abuse diminish the quality of life, hindering societal progress and obstructing human development.

Strategies for Combating Illicit Drug Use: A Holistic Approach

Drug abuse has long been a societal issue, driven by factors such as peer pressure, curiosity, easy access to drugs, and adolescent-parent dynamics (Masese, 2020, p. 1), hence, effective policy interventions and government initiatives are essential for combating illicit drug use, focusing on prevention, treatment, and rehabilitation. These should include enhanced law enforcement, improved access to addiction services, education campaigns, and socio-economic support systems to address the root causes of drug abuse. Additionally, collaboration between government agencies,

NGOs, and faith-based organisations is key to creating a coordinated, sustainable response that supports both prevention and long-term recovery. Pentecostal Christian drug treatment approaches in Nigeria show a 70% abstinence rate six months after discharge, with low re-admission rates and successful social reintegration (Adelekan & Lawal, 2006, pp. 119-129). In Nigeria, Christianity and Islam influence perceptions of substance use and mental health, with both religions endorsing the "moral model." This model sees addiction as a consequence of willingly straying from religious values, rather than being viewed as a disease (Abdalla, 2008). The Muslim world faces challenges with both drug and non-drug addictions. Islamic teachings stress preserving mental and physical health by avoiding harmful substances and play a crucial role in addiction prevention, treatment, and recovery (Ibrahim, Ayinla, & Gidado, 2024, p. 19). Hisbah is an Islamic police force in Northern Nigeria created to enforce Shari'a law and address substance abuse. The term "*hisbah*," from Arabic, refers to actions performed for the welfare of others, seeking God's reward, grounded in Qur'anic teachings and hadith (Uzobo, Yusuf & Scent, 2024, p. 37-52). Outcomes include drug abstinence, vocational rehabilitation, social reintegration, and enhanced religious involvement. Moreover, Nigerian values are institutionalised principles that influence individuals' life patterns and actions, aligning with societal goals and expectations. These values serve as benchmarks for justifying actions within the community (Sogolo, 1993).

Moral flaws like stubbornness, greed, and weak religious commitment were frequently cited as factors contributing to the development of addiction (Ebiti & Ike, 2019, p. 128). Community-based and faith-centred programs play a key role in combating illicit drug use by offering local support, counselling, and culturally relevant interventions. These programs incorporate religious teachings and community solidarity to promote healthy lifestyles, reduce stigma, and aid in addiction recovery. Religion, as a social institution, shapes values, meanings, moral codes, and notions of right and wrong, serving as a shared ground for both rich and poor in Nigeria (Samuel & Ogbu, 2017, p. 28). However (Hartz (2005), argues that "spiritual approaches to treatment are increasingly recognised due to the limitations of pharmacological and psychological therapies and the growing importance of spirituality as part of a person's cultural identity in clinical practice." By focusing on early intervention, strengthening family bonds,

and collaborating with local organisations, these programs create a supportive environment for prevention, long-term recovery, and a healthier, drug-free society.

Drug use among realistic users is controlled and balanced with life commitments, viewed as supplementary and unique, unlike archetypal users who see it as a normalised part of daily life (Notley, 2005, p. 284). Notwithstanding, education and public awareness campaigns are crucial in addressing illicit drug use by informing the public about its dangers and promoting healthy behaviours. Social inclusion involves the processes and policies that foster social cohesion and productivity for sustainability. It refers to both the outcome and process of improving how individuals and groups engage in society (Bouma, 2016, pp. 1–2). Therefore, these campaigns should be culturally relevant and targeted at schools, communities, and media platforms to engage diverse audiences and reduce stigma around addiction. Psychodynamic counselling, based on Freud's psychoanalysis, explores unconscious processes shaping thoughts and behaviours, helping clients uncover and understand their hidden inner world (Howard, 2006). By involving key stakeholders and focusing on the long-term consequences of drug abuse, such initiatives can encourage informed decisions, foster prevention, and create a supportive environment for individuals seeking help.

Discussion of the Findings

Religious traditions in Nigeria, including Christianity, Islam, and African Traditional Religion, largely view drug use as morally and spiritually wrong. Their teachings shape societal attitudes and influence policies through advocacy and religious authority. Drug abuse negatively affects education, employment, mental health, and social stability. It leads to school dropout, reduced job prospects, psychological disorders, and increased social unrest. Faith-based groups contribute significantly to drug rehabilitation and reintegration through spiritual and communal support, though they face challenges like inadequate funding, training, and lingering social stigma. Government and NGO responses show progress but often lack alignment with cultural and religious values, limiting their effectiveness in deeply religious communities. A viable intervention model must integrate religious insights, human development goals, and policy action, ensuring

community involvement, cultural relevance, and sustainable recovery outcomes.

Conclusion

This research examines the socio-cultural and religious dimensions of illicit drug use in Nigeria, investigating how societal norms, religious teachings, and community initiatives shape prevention and recovery efforts. The study reveals that while religious and cultural values play a significant role in discouraging drug abuse, the increasing influence of socio-economic challenges and peer pressure calls for a more integrated approach.

The findings highlight peer influence and socio-economic challenges as key factors driving drug use, while faith-based interventions have proven successful in encouraging abstinence and supporting rehabilitation. The findings contribute to academic discourse by highlighting the effectiveness of faith-based and community-driven interventions in combating drug abuse and promoting sustainable, drug-free communities.

Recommendations

1. ***Strengthening Community-Based and Faith-Centred Programmes:*** Community-based and faith-centred programs are effective in addressing drug abuse by offering culturally relevant support and fostering unity through religious teachings and community values. These programs benefit individuals struggling with addiction, their families, and the broader community by enhancing support networks and improving access to rehabilitation services.
2. ***Enhanced Collaboration Between Government, NGOs, and Faith-Based Organisations:*** To effectively tackle drug abuse, a multi-sectoral approach is necessary, and promoting collaboration between government bodies, NGOs, and religious institutions ensures a coordinated response that offers comprehensive care for those affected. This integrated strategy supports individuals battling drug abuse, healthcare professionals, and communities by combining enforcement, prevention, and treatment efforts.
3. ***Implementation of Public Education and Awareness Campaigns Targeting Youth:*** Early education is crucial in preventing drug use, particularly among youth. Public awareness campaigns that emphasise the dangers of substance abuse and provide alternative coping

mechanisms by promotion of healthier lifestyle choices. can significantly reduce drug use, benefiting youth, schools, and communities.

4. ***Investment in Socio-Economic Support Programs for Vulnerable Populations:*** Socio-economic factors like poverty, unemployment, and lack of education play a key role in driving drug abuse. By investing in job creation, education, and poverty alleviation programs, vulnerable groups, such as youth and low-income families, can gain better opportunities, reducing their risk of addiction.
5. ***Establishment of Comprehensive Rehabilitation and Mental Health Services:*** Access to comprehensive rehabilitation and mental health support is crucial for individuals recovering from addiction. Expanding services that offer both medical and psychological care will improve long-term recovery and decrease relapse rates, benefiting individuals, healthcare providers, and society as a whole.

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